

Table S1. Traits quantified to determine myrmecomorphy, after Kelly et al. (2021).

Characteristic	Quantification formula	Note
1: Thin legs	1 – width leg III femur / length leg III femur	-
2: Elongation of cephalothorax	1 – cephalothorax width / cephalothorax length	-
3: Elongation of abdomen	1 – abdomen width / abdomen length	-
4: Elongation of pedicel	pedicel length / total body length	-
5: Constriction of the cephalothorax	1 – cephalothorax width at point of constriction / cephalothorax width at widest point	in dorsal view
6: Constriction of the cephalothorax	1 – cephalothorax height at point of constriction / cephalothorax height at highest point	in lateral view
7: Constriction of the abdomen	1 – abdomen width at point of constriction / abdomen width at widest point	in dorsal view
8: Constriction of the abdomen	1 – abdomen height at point of constriction / abdomen height at highest point	in lateral view
9: Illusion by coloration	i) transverse band or stripe of lightly colored setae on the cephalothorax creating the illusion of a separation into a head and thorax	scored based on the presence of the illusion by coloration traits i-iii (i.e., single trait = 0.334, two traits = 0.667, and all three traits = 1.0)

ii) transverse band or stripe of lightly colored setae on the abdomen creating the illusion of a separation into a petiole (or postpetiole) and abdomen

iii) darkening of the area surrounding the posterior lateral eye creating the illusion of only two large compound eyes

Overall mimic accuracy

(A + B + C + D + E + F + G + H + I) / 9